

Job Satisfaction and Leadership on Performance

Wilson Bangun, Lina Anatan, Syela Chrissa

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of job satisfaction and leadership style on performance at Conventional Banks in Bandung, either partially or simultaneously. This research was conducted on 100 employees of bank X in Bandung. To determine the number of samples used the Slovin formula, obtained as 78 employees. The sampling technique was simple random sampling by means of lottery. To test the hypothesis is done by using the multiple regression formula. The results showed that there was an effect of Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style on Performance, either partially or simultaneously. Some employees of Bank X consider that there is unfair treatment in various ways so that Job Satisfaction is at a sufficient level. Likewise, certain indicators on the Leadership style variable are still not in accordance with the current situation. Keyword: Job Satisfaction, Style of Leadership, Performance.

Introduction

The success of a company to achieve its goals depends on how a company carries out its daily activities and is integrated into all organizational components. Achieving company goals efficiently and effectively will lead to changes that require planned efforts. Therefore, behavior in a company needs to be managed properly so that each component can run well.

Human resources are an important part that must be managed properly because they have the most strategic elements in the organization. The contribution of human resources to achieve its objectives effectively and efficiency must be measured quantitatively. Mathis and Jackson (2001) point out that a study of small US firms has found an association between these best human resource practices and lower job outcomes. This fact can be seen further which results in efforts to increase the profitability and market value of the company. Work results become a measure commonly used to measure performance both individually and in groups. Of course a company has set work standards to be the responsibility of every worker and group. Work results and work standards are comparisons that become gaps that can be measured so that the term performance appears.

In general, performance can be interpreted as the relationship between work results and work standards. Improved performance is something that is desired by both workers and employers. Employers have an interest in improving work to improve company performance which results in company profitability. On the other hand, workers' interest in improving performance is to increase self-development and job promotion. Performance is a comparison between production results and work standards over a certain period of time (Bangun, 2012). In relation to achieving company goals, a good performance management system is needed. Performance management system is the process of identifying, measuring, and assessing individual performance (Bangun, 2012).

A Commercial banks in the city of Bandung are very competitive to get customers, therefore banking companies carry out various strategies to compete in the market. Bank X is one of the private commercial banks in the city of Bandung is experiencing a decline in employee performance. Some of Bank X's employees did not achieve their job targets. Job satisfaction is one of the determinants of individual performance in a company. Therefore, job satisfaction obtained by employees in the company is a symptom for the success of a company. Research on the causes and sources of job satisfaction allows the emergence of efforts to pay attention to individual happiness in the company.

Job satisfaction of an employee feels his work is a generalization of attitudes towards his work based on various aspects of his work. This attitude is a reflection of experiences that provide pleasure and displeasure in his work, as well as his hopes for his experiences in the future (Wexley and Yukl, 2003).

Another determining factor that often causes ups and downs in performance is leadership style. Although leadership is not the main factor in solving the problem of achieving company goals, it can be used as a key factor in comparing healthy or unhealthy companies. Bennis (2006) that a company fails to achieve its goals due to over-managed or under-managed. Lately, the leadership factor is very important to consider in banking companies in Indonesia. Inappropriate leadership style will have an impact on individual performance in banking companies. Leadership style in banking companies greatly determines employee performance. This

study aims to determine the effect of job satisfaction on performance at Bank X, either partially or simultaneously.

Job Satisfaction, Leadership, and Performance

Performance appraisal is very important both for the employees themselves and for the company. Performance appraisal is an activity to evaluate the work that has been achieved by employees against the achievement standards that have been determined by the company. Cherrington (1995) explains that the purpose of an organization is to identify training needs for the benefit of employees so that the level of ability and expertise in a job can be increased at a higher level. Various research results show that individual performance is influenced by various factors, including Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style.

Job satisfaction is inherent in every job where every worker will feel whether the job is pleasant or unpleasant for every worker. Not all types of work can be judged to give the same feeling to every worker. Job characteristics differ from one job to another (Bangun, 2006). Therefore, it is a policy for every leader to match the characteristics of the job with the abilities of the workers. This conformity will cause feelings of pleasure or displeasure, causing satisfaction or dissatisfaction for the stakeholders. Wexley and Yukl (2012) explain that job satisfaction is the generalization of attitudes towards work. Job satisfaction can be assessed based on the amount of workers' contributions to their work with the results they receive (Bangun, 2012).

Schermerchorn (2002) menjelaskan bahwa kepemimpinan adalah proses mengarahkan dalam menginspirasi orang lain agar mampu bekerja keras dalam menjalankan fungsinya. Sehubungan dengan pendapat para ahli lain dalam kepemimpinan menggunakan istilah membujuk orang lain (Locke, 2002), mempengaruhi orang lain agar termotivasi dan antusias (Koontz, Donnell, Weihreich, 2005). Robins (2005) menggunakan istilah mempengaruhi kelompok lain. Berdasarkan hal tersebut, bahwa pada hakikatnya kepemimpinan adalah suatu usaha yang dilakukan oleh manajer dengan menggunakan fungsi kepemimpinan untuk mempengaruhi para pengikutnya agar melaksanakan tugasnya sesuai dengan fungsinya dalam organisasi.

Basically job satisfaction is an individual thing. Each individual will have a different level of satisfaction according to the value system that applies to him. This is due to differences in each individual. Job satisfaction is an effective or emotional reaction of employees in dealing with work with results that can be compared between the income received and the expectation of the award obtained (Stoner, 1992).

Job satisfaction obtained by employees in the company is a symptom for the success of a company. Job satisfaction is basically a positive and pleasant response as a response or feedback to his work. Robins (2001) says that, Job Satisfaction refers to the general attitude of an individual towards his job. A person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards performance, on the other hand someone who is dissatisfied with his job shows a negative attitude towards the job.

Several studies have shown that job satisfaction and performance influence each other with different positions between the independent and dependent variables. It is said to have a continuous influence because not always satisfied employees have high performance (John W. Newstrom & Keith Davis, 1993). On the one hand, employees feel satisfied because they have high work results. On the other hand, high-performing employees lead to job satisfaction. The position of the two variables depends on the focus of the research to be carried out.

Some research results show that high job satisfaction will improve individual performance. Increasing job satisfaction can be done through a reward system which results in increased performance (Amstrong, 1987). The reward system aims to foster morale which results in increased performance. Leadership is an important concept to measure the success of an organization in achieving its goals. A leader in an organization has a very important role in setting strategy. This has become an activity carried out by leaders consistently to be able to give serious attention to fostering, encouraging, and mobilizing all organizational resources appropriately to obtain efficient and effective work results.

Kouzes (2004) explains that the leader is the first person to bring the organization to step in an uncertain situation. This relates to the vision as a guide to bring an organization in a clear direction. Maxwell (1995) explains that leadership is nothing more and nothing less to influence followers. Robins (2006) explains that leadership is the ability to influence groups in achieving organizational goals. Bangun (2008) explains that leadership is a process to direct and influence others in order to carry out their duties properly in achieving organizational goals.

Each leader in the organization carries out its duties in a different style depending on the situation and characteristics of the subordinates. Leadership style is how a leader influences subordinates. Stoner (1995) explains that leadership style shows the behavior of a leader in influencing and directing employees. Likewise, Boone, Kuntz, and Berston (2019) explain that leadership style is the way a leader uses power to influence others.

Hypothesis:

1. Job Satisfaction has an effect on performance.

2. Leadership Style has an effect on Performance.
3. Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style Simultaneously Affect Performance

Method

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

This research was conducted at Bank X in the city of Bandung for all permanent employees totaling 100 people. Due to limited time and funds, this population was sampled using the Slovin formula, as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Based on this formula, the number of samples is 80 employees. The sampling technique was carried out using a simple random sample (simple random sampling). Data collection techniques were carried out by means of questionnaires, interviews, and observations.

Data analysis method

To analyze the data in this study, multiple regression was used. Multiple regression is a linear regression model that has more than 1 independent variable. Multiple regression analysis is used to predict how far the influence of one or several independent variables (X) on the dependent variable (Y), where the general form of multiple linear regression can be explained through the following regression equation model:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2$$

Where: Y = dependent variable (Performance), a = Constant b_1 = Regression coefficient of independent variable 1 (Job Satisfaction) b_2 = Regression coefficient of independent variable 2 (Leadership Style) X_1 = Independent variable 1 (Job Satisfaction) X_2 = Independent variable 2 (Leadership Style)..

Results and Discussion

In testing the hypothesis using regression analysis to determine the effect of Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style on Performance either partially or simultaneously. The results of testing the hypothesis are shown in Table 1.

Tabel 1. Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-7.641	8.412		-.908	.367
	Leadership Style	1.994	.200	.752	9.957	.000
2	(Constant)	-2.704	7.830		-.345	.731
	Leadership Style	1.468	.228	.554	6.424	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.407	.105	.335	3.886	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Table 1 shows that the equation for multiple linear regression is $Y = -2.704 + 0.407X_1 + 1.468X_2$. This equation shows that the constant value is -2.704, meaning that if the performance is not influenced by the two variables, namely Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style, then the performance is -2.704. The coefficient of job satisfaction with a value of 0.407 indicates that job satisfaction has an effect on performance. Each increase in the Job Satisfaction variable by 1% will increase performance by 0.407 percent. Likewise, every increase in the Leadership Style variable, it will increase Performance by 1.468 percent.

Table 2 shows that the variables of Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style are predictors of performance. This can be seen based on the calculated F value of 66,318 with a significance level of 0.000. Based on the value of sig 0.05, this indicates that the regression model can be used to predict performance with a hypothesis.

Tabel 2. ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9539.817	1	9539.817	99.147	.000 ^b
	Residual	7312.644	76	96.219		
	Total	16852.462	77			
2	Regression	10765.227	2	5382.614	66.318	.000 ^c

Residual	6087.234	75	81.163		
Total	16852.462	77			

- a. Dependent Variable: Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style
- c. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style, Job Satisfaction

In the following, partial hypothesis testing will be presented on the first and second hypotheses, and simultaneously on the third hypothesis. The first hypothesis, based on statistical results shows that Job Satisfaction has a $\text{sig.} = 0.000 < 0.05$. This means that job satisfaction has an effect on performance. Table 2 shows that the coefficient obtained that the t count for the Job Satisfaction variable is 3.886 which is greater than t table of 1.994, this indicates that Job Satisfaction has a significant effect on performance. The higher the level of job satisfaction in a company will increase individual performance. The results of this study indicate how important it is to create high job satisfaction in the company. The high level of Job Satisfaction shows the comfort and pleasure of employees towards their work to achieve the goals set by Bank X. Job Satisfaction describes how employees feel comfortable and pleasant work on their work. Bangun (2018) defines that Job Satisfaction shows how every employee likes his job which can be seen from their loyalty to his job. Pleasant work is a characteristic that the employee's assessment of his work is good. This shows the high level of Job Satisfaction as an assessment of each worker. Job satisfaction is very important to note because it can be used as a generalization on employee attitudes towards work (Yukl, 2003). Every human being has a different attitude in assessing work which is reflected in a pleasant work experience and every expectation of the job (Bangun, 2016). A pleasant job will provide job satisfaction which results in work plans through supervision related to work (Louis A. Allen, 1987). Thus, job satisfaction can be used as a measure of the function of values, perceptions, differences for workers in what they should receive (Noe, et al, 1997).

The second hypothesis, shows that t count of 9.957 is greater than t table of 1.994, this indicates that the Leadership Style variable has an effect on performance. Leadership style is an important factor in influencing employees to be able to carry out their activities well (Bangun, 2019). Managers in carrying out their functions as leaders are expected to be able to manage the company by selecting and allocating all organizational resources properly (Bangun, 2021). One important factor, the appropriate leadership style will improve individual performance (Bangun, 2021). The employer really needs to build a suitability of the leadership style applied by the company, because it will determine performance.

The third hypothesis, testing simultaneously between Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style on Performance. Based on the statistical results in Table 3, it is obtained that the R square value of 0.639 with a significant value of 0.00 is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$ which indicates that Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style simultaneously have a significant effect on performance. This figure shows that Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style significantly affect the performance of 63.9 percent. There are other factors that affect the performance of 36.1 percent. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct future research on what factors affect the performance of Bank X.

Tabel 4.7. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.752 ^a	.566	.560	9.809
2	.799 ^b	.639	.629	9.009

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style, Job Satisfaction

Various studies place that performance is the dependent variable which is influenced by the independent variables. In this study, performance is influenced by job satisfaction and leadership style, which means that the relationship between the three variables is causal. Performance appraisal is a process carried out by an organization in assessing or evaluating the success of an organization in achieving its goals (Bangun, 2021). In accordance with this, every company needs to increase job satisfaction and suitability of leadership style, because these two variables are factors to improve performance.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the descriptive and explanatory analysis of this study, conclusions will be drawn. The descriptive results show that the level of Job Satisfaction at Bank X is high, this indicates that in general Bank X employees feel comfortable and enjoy working. The suitability of Bank X's Leadership Style is sufficient, this shows that in general that Bank X's Leadership Style is quite good and in accordance with current conditions. Similarly, in general, individual performance at Bank X is high.

For explanatory research, based on hypothesis testing, it is shown that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This shows that there is a strong influence between Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style on Performance both partially and simultaneously. Partially, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance. This shows that the higher the level of job satisfaction will increase individual performance. Leadership Style has a positive and significant effect on performance, this shows that the more appropriate the leadership style will increase individual performance at Bank X. The results of this study indicate that simultaneously, Job Satisfaction and Leadership Style will simultaneously affect individual performance at Bank X.

Based on the conclusions of this study, there are several suggestions, among others, on each variable. For the Job Satisfaction variable: as an indicator of this variable, there are still several indicators that need to be considered related to Job Satisfaction at Bank X. Some of these indicators include work that does not require a variety of knowledge and skills. This will cause work boredom, therefore it is necessary to do job rotation, job enrichment and job enlargement. A small number of employees do not understand their work well, this happens because the employee does not want to develop himself. For the Leadership Style variable, a small part of the application of the Leadership Style is authoritarian which causes saturation for employees. Therefore, the management of Bank X must be able to adapt to the situation of technological developments.

Recommendations

Berdasarkan hasil penelitian ini, perusahaan perlu memperhatikan karyawan yang memiliki kinerja rendah. Mereka perlu mendapatkan pengembangan, baik berupa peningkatan pendidikan maupun pelatihan. Pegawai Bank X di Bandung membutuhkan peningkatan kompensasi berupa bonus dan insentif. Demikian pula manajemen perusahaan perlu membuat aturan dan regulasi yang jelas terkait budaya perusahaan yang kuat untuk meningkatkan kinerja.

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Author Information

Wilson Bangun

Maranatha Christian University
Jl. Surya Sumantri No. 65 Bandung

Lina Anatan

Maranatha Christian University
Jl. Surya Sumantri No. 65 Bandung

SyelaChrissa

Student of Master of Management at Maranatha
Christian University
Jl. Surya Sumantri No. 65 Bandung
